

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP7 - Communication and Dissemination Articles series: “Common Grounds”

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E-mail address	: pierre.mounier@openedition.org , alessia.smaniotto@openedition.org
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Authors	: Gabrielle Goyer, Cafebabel Quentin Ariès, Cafebabel Kaan Yildirim, Max Weber Stiftung
Proofreading	: Kelly Achenbach, Max Weber Stiftung Marlen Töpfer, Max Weber Stiftung

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I. Introduction

Summary

This deliverable provides the details of an article series entitled “Common Grounds,” which was created and published on the [Cafebabel website](#) as part of the COESO project’s communication and dissemination activities. Included in this document is a brief description of COESO, a description of each of the five articles, their publication dates, links to read the articles on the Cafebabel website, and their permanent DOI address, where they are published (open access) on Zenodo.

COESO Overview

The COESO project (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues)¹ is a 3-year participatory research project, funded by the European Commission through a Science with and for Society grant, and supported by the OPERAS Research Infrastructure². The COESO project contributes to overcoming the obstacles that hinder the development of citizen science in the social sciences and humanities and facilitates and supports participatory research through a service-first approach. The project develops the Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation (VERA), a collaborative place for knowledge production and sharing, and collaborates with research funding organizations to enhance financial support for citizen science. At the heart of the project are ten citizen science pilots, representing a variety of social sciences and humanities disciplines, societal challenges and types of engagement with citizens in different European countries. The ten pilots address diverse specific societal issues: mass tourism, education and gender, resilient societies, fight against crime, societal change and migration, inclusivity in city planning, valorisation of aging people in communities, accessing and using local knowledge and leadership for policy making/implementation, raising awareness on climate change, and food insecurities of children. Overall, COESO serves as a meeting point between various European communities: the social sciences and humanities community, the citizen science community, as well as the open scholarly communication community. In this bridging endeavor, COESO is synergising with existing communities such as Hypotheses.org³ and EU-Citizen.Science⁴. Moreover, it is exploring the frontiers of innovation in the social sciences and humanities’ public engagement through mutual learning exercises with the pilot projects and through experimentations with multimedia research outputs. Furthermore, to measure the quality of collaboration between researchers and citizens, COESO is designing a framework and corresponding code for a tool called *Cooperation Analytics*. More about the COESO project can be found on the project website: coeso.hypotheses.org.

Within the COESO project, the communication and dissemination work package (WP7) engages with stakeholders to communicate the project results and outputs through a variety of communication channels, including the “Common Grounds” article series, which showcases COESO outputs, especially those related to the ten pilot projects and the VERA hub.

¹ See <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006325>

² See <https://www.operas-eu.org/>

³ See <https://hypotheses.org/>

⁴ See <https://eu-citizen.science/>

II. “Common Ground” articles series

The “Common Grounds” article series is part of COESO’s work package 7, in fulfillment of the task 7.4 “Realisation of podcasts and article series.” The overarching theme of the articles is how to build bridges between research and civil society. Four of the articles were conceptualized, developed and produced between January 2022 and October 2023 in collaboration with Cafebabel journalists and with the help of the COESO coordination team. The final article was written by a staff member at the Max Weber Foundation, published in December 2023.

Babel International is a European NGO, officially aiming to develop European citizenship through media literacy and the online magazine Cafebabel since 2001. Cafebabel is the first multilingual paneuropean magazine, read by 280,000 unique visitors across Europe each month. Cafebabel is considered one of the most important European platforms in the promotion of participatory journalism thanks to its non-institutional vision of Europe. Indeed, one of the main assets of the editorial line is to talk about “Europe in real life”. The team is composed of professional editors and journalists in Paris, Brussels, Rome and Berlin. In August 2023, Babel International merged with Erebus Media to sail towards new European horizons and embark on a new adventure. This new publication, as an experiment, was launched in mid-2021. The Cafebabel website, including all of its articles, are permanently available online, and all new articles are now being published on ereb.eu.

Article Series Summary

“Common Grounds” explores how social sciences and humanities researchers are collaborating with civil society actors and journalists. The articles feature how these stakeholders jointly explore new ways to investigate social issues, share their research, and improve their impact. The goal of the series was to spread knowledge, to a general audience, about the potential that citizen science has to help solve societal issues. It sought to highlight the diverse, but complementary, approaches used by different stakeholders to achieve common goals. The series focused on cross-cutting issues touched upon by the different COESO pilots: building trusting relationships, the role of collaboration to solve societal issues, and the role of NGOs and associations in citizen science. In total, five original articles were produced and published on the Cafebabel website; the first four articles were written originally in French and translated into English and Italian. The fifth article is available only in English.

Full articles from the “Common Grounds” series can be found at the following links on the Cafebabel website:

- Article 1: ([EN](#)/[FR](#)/[IT](#))
- Article 2: ([EN](#)/[FR](#)/[IT](#))
- Article 3: ([EN](#)/[FR](#)/[IT](#))
- Article 4: ([EN](#)/[FR](#)/[IT](#))
- Article 5: ([EN](#))

Article Descriptions

Terrains Communs

Article 1: Uncovering the lives of first generation immigrants, letter by letter

D'une lettre à l'autre, des égo- histoires d'exils

Published on April 17, 2023 – by Cafébabel

First publication date: April 17, 2023

Author: Quentin Ariès (Cafébabel)

Link:

<https://cafebabel.com/en/article/uncovering-the-lives-of-first-generation-immigrants-letter-by-letter-64463753c08424e31ecaac14/>

More than ten million Germans crossed the Atlantic Ocean for the New World in the 19th and 20th centuries. According to various censuses, more than 43 million American citizens have German origins, and yet their ancestors' stories remain relatively unknown. Historians are working

with citizens in COESO's pilot 5, "[Growing migrant knowledge: contemporary and historical perspectives](#)." to fill this gap in historical records and to better understand the daily lives of these first generation immigrants. And this is the focus of the first article in the "Common Grounds" series.

Article 2: Researchers are working with local communities to make a tangible impact

Quand les chercheurs s'associent avec la société pour renforcer leurs impacts concrets

Published on April 20, 2023 – by Cafébabel

First publication date: April 20, 2023

Author: Léa Marchal (Cafebabel)

Link:

<https://cafebabel.com/en/article/researchers-are-working-with-local-communities-to-make-a-tangible-impact-64464a1b383ae5868134a53f/>

Very often, researchers and scientists complain that their worlds seem closed off and hard to understand by the rest of the society. Could collaborations with local communities therefore be the magic solution to bringing the world of research down from its ivory tower? For this feature, which is part of the "Common Grounds" series, Cafebabel headed to Tanzania where COESO's pilot #8, "[Women Water Watch](#)" uses citizen science to help local communities better manage their water resources and engage with policy issues.

Article 3: The researcher-journalist duo, the recipe for a top notch investigation

Le couple chercheur - journaliste, la recette pour creuser les sujets

Published on August 30, 2023 – by Cafébabel

First publication date: August 30, 2023

Author: Léa Marchal (Cafebabel)

Link:

<https://cafebabel.com/en/article/the-researcher-journalist-duo-the-recipe-for-a-top-notch-investigation-64fa00e21379ad98a84cfb55/>

Social science researchers work over the long term. Journalists, on the other hand, have a vocation to follow the newscycle. But can they collaborate hand-in-hand on long-term projects? For the third article in the “Common Grounds” series, Cafebabel visits COESO’s pilot #3, “[Social impacts of redistributing property confiscated from the mafia](#)”, in Italy to explore the relationship between journalists and researchers.

Article 4: Citizen science and sensitive subjects: the example of mass tourism

Science citoyenne et sujets sensibles: l'exemple du tourisme de masse

Published on October 16, 2023 – by Cafébabel

First publication date: October 16, 2023

Author: Quentin Ariès (Cafebabel)

Link:

<https://cafebabel.com/fr/article/science-citoyenne-et-sujets-sensibles-lexemple-du-tourisme-de-masse-651eba5726fe038ac044d23a/>

There's often a cliché that researchers, including those in the social sciences and humanities, find it hard to get out of their ivory towers. That scientists have difficulties opening up to society, and that they remain confined to their research. But this is clearly not the case. Across Europe, researchers and associations are working together on concrete projects, even on socially sensitive subjects. For this article of the “Common Grounds” series, Cafebabel sailed to Lisbon where researchers from COESO's pilot #1, “[Mass tourism's impact on urban communities](#)” from the anthropology research center CRIA worked in the San Antonio neighborhood with the environmental association ZERO to study the impact of tourism development in the area.

Article 5: Empowering inclusive communities: Citizen science for vulnerable populations in Europe

Empowering Inclusive Communities: Citizen Science Unites for Vulnerable Populations in Europe

Published on December 11, 2023

First publication date: December 11, 2023

Author: Kagan Yildirim (Max Weber Stiftung)

Link: [Empowering Inclusive Communities: Citizen Science Unites for Vulnerable Populations in Europe \(cafebabel.com\)](https://cafebabel.com/article/empowering-inclusive-communities-citizen-science-unites-for-vulnerable-populations-in-europe)

In Germany, the COESO pilot #6, DiMDiCi, involves citizens, including those with cognitive disabilities, in shaping urban planning through an interactive mapping tool. Simultaneously in Italy, the COESO pilot #7 [AGORAge](#) focuses on social inclusion for older adults. Both projects exemplify citizen science's transformative impact on community development, emphasizing inclusivity. Challenges, such as sustaining engagement, are acknowledged, highlighting the pivotal role of third-party organizations in overcoming obstacles. Ultimately, these initiatives showcase how citizen science empowers communities to actively contribute to shaping their environments.

III Dissemination Overview

Each article, upon publication, was made permanently available on the Cafebabel website and links to those that were already written were included in Cafebabel's newsletter, which has a database of 18,864 emails, in May 2023, October 2023, and November 2023. Additionally, COESO

posted multiple tweets about each article on the project's Twitter/X, and published a summarizing blogpost (<https://coeso.hypotheses.org/7351>) about the article series on the COESO website. As of November 23, 2023, the links to the articles from the newsletter had been clicked as follows:

- Article 1 French: 420 clicks
- Article 1 English: 193 clicks
- Article 1 Italian: 88 clicks
- Article 2 French: 352 clicks
- Article 2 English: 256 clicks
- Article 2 Italian: 94 clicks
- Article 3 French: 252 clicks
- Article 3 English: 145 clicks
- Article 3 Italian: 60 clicks
- Article 4 French: 125 clicks
- Article 4 English: 130 clicks
- Article 4 Italian: 25 clicks
- [Note: Article 5 was not published until December and therefore statistics on it are not available at the time of writing the report]